

A GAN-Augmented Multi-Scale CNN for Blight Detection and Classification in Solanaceous Crops

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Abstract— Plant disease is one of the most concerning problems in agriculture as it presents a very serious threat to crop production and global food security. The most common type of disease in solanaceous crops such as potato and tomato is the leaf blight disease which appears in different visual forms ranging from small brown spots to large lesions. Automated disease detection is still challenging because of lack of balanced, high-quality dataset and disease variation across plant species. To address these limitations, this research proposes Tri-ScaleNet, a unified framework that integrates a Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) for data augmentation with a Multi-Scale Multi-Head Convolution Neural Network (MSMH-CNN) for disease classification. The cGAN generates realistic synthetic images by maintaining disease specific textures, lesion boundaries and colour variation. Then MSMH-CNN is used to extract features using parallel convolution kernels of different sizes, enabling the model to detect small scale spots as well as large decaying areas. Experimental finding reveals that our proposed method yields a strong performance with a validation accuracy of 98.62% across all classes. Additionally, we have used Grad-CAM visualization to demonstrate that model concentrates on disease-affected areas, which increases transparency and user trust by visualizing the decision processes, enhancing its effectiveness and potential usefulness in precision agriculture.

Keywords—Plant disease detection, Conditional GAN (cGAN), Data Augmentation, Deep Learning, Convolution Neural Network, Explainable AI, Grad-CAM, Leaf Blight.

I. INTRODUCTION

Plant diseases pose a silent but very dangerous menace to global food security and they often remain unnoticed until agronomic damage has been incurred. Potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*) and tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*) are among the most widely cultivated crops with extreme sensitivity towards destructive diseases such as Early Blight caused by *Alternaria solani* (a fungal pathogen) and Late Blight caused by *phytophthora infestans* (an oomycete) [4,5,10]. Late diagnosis of such diseases triggers a rapid decline in yields and food production. Traditional methods of identification rely on manual scouting by experts, a process that is labor-intensive, subjective and often too slow to prevent widespread outbreaks [15]. Recent advancements in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) such as improved accuracy and speed, have

significantly enhanced image-based plant disease detection [1, 16]. However, there still remains two main challenges that can limit their use in the agricultural setting. First, public datasets are often small and inclined towards healthy samples leading to overfitting and poor generalization [11, 12]. Second, there are pathological features that arise at different spatial scales for example, early blight contains small concentric spots but late blight has large irregular necrotic spots. Standard CNNs with fixed receptive fields (3X3) struggle to capture this multiscale diversity effectively [3].

To address the above limitations, this paper proposes Tri-ScaleNet, a novel architecture that combines generative data augmentation with scale-invariant disease classification. Firstly, a conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN) is utilized to generate realistic biologically synthetic leaf images, hence reducing the issue of class imbalance [17-19]. These augmented images are then used to train the multi-scale multi-head CNN (MSMH-CNN) that combines feature representation from different kernel dimensions with a wide range of spatial scales for powerful and reliable detection of diseases.

In light of the growing demand for food, climate unpredictability and limited agricultural inputs, the development of systems like Tri-ScaleNet becomes increasingly important for digital plant monitoring. This is also the reason for rise in intelligent systems that supports uninterrupted and massive monitoring of crop health using smartphones, drones or field cameras [7, 13]. These systems allow cultivators to detect pathogens early, reduce unnecessary pesticide use and facilitate evidence-based, timely agronomic interventions to boost yield and prevent economic loss [6]. At the national level, smart crop surveillance supports sustainable agriculture, enhances food security and helps government agencies in monitoring crop health and organizing strategic interventions effectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, new developments in precision agriculture have been more concerned with optimizing the deep learning architectures to address the challenges of crop disease detection. Chohan et al. developed a fine-tuned VGG16 neural network to detect tomato leaf disease, achieving high accuracy by changing the weight parameters of the neural network [1]. Although they have performed well in a standard architecture but their methodology is based on a fixed receptive field which restricts the capability of the model to identify small early-stage spots and bigger lesions at the later stage simultaneously. Deng et al. had

developed RAHC_GAN, a special Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) model that uses attention mechanism to generate data and helps the model to focus on the disease spots instead of the whole leaf. This enabled them to create very realistic synthetic tomato leaf images which resolved the problem of data deficiency [2]. Zhang et al. introduced Tranvolution network which combined Transformer attention with GAN modules to improve detection abilities [3]. While their approaches proved to be very efficient in detecting complex features but it has very high computational resources making it harder for edge deployment.

Later, the studies focused on hybrid systems that can handle several crops. Patil et al. designed a hybrid model that combined an optimized CNN and optimized LSTM to classify diseases of potato and tomato crops, achieving high accuracy [4]. In spite of high performance of these models, they depended mostly on common data augmentation methods (such as rotation, filtering, attenuation) which do not tend to replicate real-life, complicated disease variants that can be generated using a generative method. Sharma et al. investigated a combination of deep learning with Support Vector Machines (SVM) in case of weakly supervised scenarios in which the data labels are not perfect [5]. Although this hybrid approach was more stable, its accuracy was lower than those of pure end-to-end deep learning models in cases where data is sufficient. Alhammad et al. used a DenseNet121 architecture to classify potato leaves, achieving a high accuracy of 98% [6]. To resolve the issue of lack of trust in AI decisions, they incorporated Grad-CAM to visually verify disease locations but they only used conventional CNN models that are unable to handle changes in scale. Moreover, Chang et al. presented a lightweight model that can be implemented on mobile devices using RegNetY-400MF and the classification accuracy of the model is 89.87% [7]. Although their model was very fast but lightweight architectures typically compromise depth to differentiate between visual similar pathogens such as *Alternaria solani* and *Phytophthora infestans*. Other researchers like Foysal et al. proved that it was not enough to rotate or invert the images. They started to experiment with GANs to do data augmentation [8]. Nonetheless, their use was frequently restricted to simple generation without the stabilization methods and thus generates lower-quality synthetic samples that could confuse the classifier.

In subsequent years, the shortcomings of the conventional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were becoming more evident. Ghosh et al. trained standard CNNs in detecting potato disease, but found that the accuracy stopped improving because of the absence of a variety of training data. They obtained decent results with their model which did not generalize well to new or unseen leaf variations [10]. This increased the importance of generative augmentation. Further reviews done by Muhammad et al. confirmed that models such as ResNet and DenseNet were successful but requires a large amount of data and can overfit when trained on small and imbalanced datasets [11]. The turning point of the generative modeling was around 2022. In their review of GAN in agriculture, Olaniyi et al. found that it offered the best solution to the data scarcity issue. Their results showed that generated images are statistically similar to real ones which justify their use in training [12]. Chen et al. implemented this idea on fruit defect detection with

CycleGAN. Though they experimented with pineapples but it still influenced agricultural researchers as it demonstrated how GANs could be used to convert images from one domain to another in order to generate varied training samples [13]. Although CycleGANs are computationally expensive and very hard to control than most models. Lamba et al. found that standard augmentation could not achieve high accuracy in paddy diseases but when a GAN was used to generate synthetic images, they increased the accuracy of their model from 92.4% to 98.23% [14]. However, their methodology maintained the separation of the classification and generation stages without optimization of the architecture of the classifier.

Earlier research and developments in 2020 and 2021 laid the foundation to work on them but faced various challenges. Trivedi et al. was one of the earliest to use high-performance Deep Neural Networks on tomato disease. Their contribution was revolutionary but depended on the traditional data collection which was labor-intensive [15]. According to a literature review conducted by David et al., the accuracy was improving but the challenge of data availability was still the single biggest barrier towards better accuracy. [16]. Jabbar et al. presented a survey of GAN variants and agricultural researchers had the theoretical framework to begin experimenting with models such as DCGAN and Conditional GANs [17]. Zeng et al. were one of the first to use Deep Convolutional GANs (DCGAN) to the work of citrus diseases with a validation accuracy of 92.6% by augmenting their training set [18]. Lastly, Gandhi et al. were one of the first pioneers who proposed using GANs as an augmentative approach [19], a visionary idea that has now become the standard in 2025.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Description

In this paper, a unified dataset was generated by combining potato and tomato leaf images from several publicly available repositories. It includes images from different datasets that added realistic differences in background, lighting and environment which is essential for learning the real disease patterns under varied conditions. The images were further classified into three classes: Early Blight (Small circular-brown spot with concentric rings on the leaf surface), Healthy (uniform green leaves without any visible spots and lesions) and Late Blight (Large irregular-dark lesion that spreads quickly through the whole leaf surface). Basic image processing steps were applied before training to improve features that are related to the disease shown in Fig. 1. It involves conversion of all the images to 128×128 pixels, enhancing contrast to ensure that boundary of the lesions could be seen, sharpening and segmentation to focus only on the disease-affected regions but still there was a significant imbalance in dataset among the three classes.

TABLE I. CLASS - WISE DATA DISTRIBUTION

Class Label	Original (Real)	Synthetic (cGAN)	Total Samples	Training Set (80%)	Testing Set (20%)
Early Blight	2000	2000	4000	3200	800
Healthy	3056	944	4000	3200	800
Late Blight	3926	74	4000	3200	800
Total	8982	3018	12000	9600	2400

In order to address the imbalance among the classes, a Conditional GAN (cGAN) was employed to produce real-world synthetic images of each class. Table I demonstrates that Late Blight has ample amount of data so it requires very minimal augmentation but Early Blight and Healthy classes required more augmentation to reach 4,000 images per class. This method helps to increase the data to 12,000 images with an equal distribution of 4,000 images per class. The final dataset was divided into 9,600 training and 2,400 testing images in a 80: 20 stratified ratio. Such balanced and enhanced feature dataset allowed the model to efficiently learn smaller disease spots as well as massive lesions patterns, which later helps the Tri-ScaleNet to classify images correctly and accurately.

Fig. 1: Data Preprocessing Techniques

B. Conditional GAN for Data Augmentation

To overcome the problem of limited data, a Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) was used to synthesize realistic images of leaves for each class. The cGAN is composed of two adversarial networks: Generator and Discriminator, which work together to learn the desired output in an adversarial way shown in Fig. 2.

The Generator takes random noise Z along with a class label as input and learns to synthesize a realistic 128×128 RGB leaf image through several upsampling layers. At the same time as if judging those generations, the Discriminator learns to differentiate between actual leaf images and synthetic ones made by the Generator.

While training, both networks improve themselves by learning from their losses. The Discriminator reduces the loss against misclassification of real and synthetic images, whereas the Generator reduces the loss that encourages it to deceive the Discriminator. As training progresses, the Generator produces increasingly realistic leaf images, while the Discriminator becomes better at identifying subtle differences, resulting in a balanced and high-quality augmented dataset well suited for Tri-ScaleNet classification.

Fig. 2: Overview of the cGAN Architecture

C. Tri-ScaleNet Classification Architecture

In this work, we introduce Tri-ScaleNet as the core classification framework, which is designed to recognize disease symptoms that appear at different sizes on leaf surfaces. Rather than using a single and fixed convolution size, Tri-ScaleNet has three different ways of looking at the image simultaneously.

Each Multi-Scale Block separates the input feature map into three parallel paths. The small 3×3 kernels detect smaller spots, the larger 5×5 kernels capture medium-level textures, and the largest 7×7 kernels identify large lesions. The data of all three directions is then combined by concatenating and refining the features with a 1×1 convolution so that the network is able to comprehend the patterns of the disease at various levels.

Fig. 3 shows the proposed architecture where the overall network stacks three Multi-Scale blocks, followed by Global Average Pooling and a Softmax layer to predict the final class. This design mirrors how disease symptoms naturally vary in size, enabling Tri-ScaleNet to accurately distinguish between Early Blight, Late Blight and Healthy leaves.

Fig. 3: Tri-ScaleNet Architecture

Fig. 4: Workflow of the overall System

D. System Overview

Fig. 4 displays the proposed framework which operates in two sequential and complementary phases designed to address both data scarcity and accurate disease classification. In the first phase, a Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) is trained to understand the visual distribution of each leaf class. By learning class-specific patterns such as spots, textures and lesion shapes, the cGAN generates realistic synthetic leaf images which are then used to balance the dataset and reduce bias caused by uneven class representation.

In the second phase, the augmented dataset which consists both real and synthetic images is used to train the Tri-ScaleNet classifier. With access to a balanced and diverse set of samples, Tri-ScaleNet learns to distinguish between healthy leaves and different disease types across multiple visual scales. The trained model is then evaluated on a separate test set to assess its generalization performance on new or unseen images.

To ensure that the model focuses on meaningful disease-related patterns rather than other background objects, Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) is used for explainability. Grad-CAM works by analyzing how strongly different regions of an image influence the model's final decision, producing a heatmap that highlights the most important areas. These visual explanations confirm that the model consistently focuses on pathological features such as disease spots and lesion regions when making predictions. Additionally, an interactive application using Streamlit is developed to make the system accessible. Using this interface, users can upload leaf pictures and immediately get the predicted disease category and the generated Grad-CAM explanation at the same time. Such a fusion of prediction and visual reasoning results in improved transparency and trust where the users not only know what the model predicts but also the reason behind it. Overall, this unified system incorporates data augmentation for better feature extraction, accurate multi-scale classification and explainable predictions. It not only helps in the detection of diseases but also provides transparency and ensures practical applicability in the real-world agricultural settings.

E. Experimental Setup

All experiments were implemented in the PyTorch framework and trained on NVIDIA P100 GPU equipped with CUDA for faster computation. The networks were optimized with Adam optimizer where learning rate was 0.0002 for cGAN to achieve stable image generation and 0.001 for Tri-ScaleNet classifier for faster convergence. For training, the loss used in cGAN was Binary Cross-Entropy loss and for disease classification it was cross-entropy loss.

A stratified 80:20 split was applied to the dataset so that each class had equal representation in the training and testing set. After training and evaluation, the final model was integrated into a Streamlit-based application where users can upload leaf images and receive instant predictions along with visual explanations. This setup bridges the gap between model development and real-world use, making the framework practical and easy to interact with.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Analysis

The proposed Tri-ScaleNet model had achieved an overall classification accuracy of 98.62%. It performs very well across all the classes, with a weighted precision of 98.63%, weighted recall of 98.62% and weighted F1-score of 98.63%. The class which performed the best amongst all the three classes was the 'Healthy' class with an F1-score of 99.56% as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE METRICS

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Early Blight	0.9913	0.9768	0.984	820
Healthy	0.995	0.9962	0.9956	796
Late Blight	0.9723	0.986	0.9791	784
Accuracy	0.9862	0.9862	0.9862	0.9862
Macro Avg	0.9862	0.9863	0.9862	2400
Weighted Avg	0.9863	0.9862	0.9863	2400

B. Confusion Matrix

In Fig. 5, the confusion matrix shows high diagonal dominance, indicating high classification accuracy across all classes. The majority of Early Blight (801/820), Healthy (793/796) and Late Blight (773/784) samples were correctly identified and there were only a few cases of misclassifications amongst visually similar disease classes. The Healthy class shows minimal confusion, demonstrating reliable separation between healthy and diseased leaves.

Fig. 5: Confusion Matrix for Disease Classification

C. ROC Curve

The Fig. 6 illustrates the one vs. rest ROC curves of the three classes. The proposed model presents high AUC values of Early Blight, Healthy and Late Blight classes as 0.9988, 0.9998 and 0.9979 respectively, which reflects its high discriminative power and consistency of the separation between different disease categories.

Fig. 6: ROC Curves of the Proposed Model

D. Training Curves

The training dynamics of our model is depicted in Fig. 7. Training and validation accuracy both steadily increases and converge, whereas the training loss continuously decreases indicating that the optimization is stable and there is no overfitting.

Fig. 7: Training accuracy and loss curves of the model

E. Explainability using Grad-CAM

Fig. 8 shows the Grad-CAM images from samples of each class. The above results indicate that Tri-ScaleNet pays more attention to the disease-related parts of the leaves, including lesion margins and areas of discoloration, whereas the focus on Healthy samples is relatively uniform. This concludes that the predictions made by the model are motivated by meaningful and interpretable features.

Fig. 8: Grad-CAM Overlays on Disease Affected Regions

F. Discussion

The results indicate that cGAN-based data augmentation is very important for improving model performance by reducing class imbalance and enhancing data diversity. Moreover, Tri-ScaleNet has maintain a high accuracy and low confusion between diseases that look similar because it is designed using multi-scale blocks to be able to identify both small disease spots and large lesion areas. Grad-CAM visualizations further support these findings by highlighting meaningful disease regions such as concentric rings for Early Blight and large necrotic patches for Late Blight even in synthetic images. This proves that the model acquires actual pathological characteristics and not background patterns, which not only confirm the credibility of augmented data but also the strength of the proposed framework.

TABLE III. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS LEAF DISEASE DETECTION TECHNIQUES

Reference	Target Crop(s)	No. of Classes	Technique/Model	Accuracy (%)
Chen et al. [13]	Pineapple	3	CycleGAN + YOLOv4	84.86
Chang et al. [7]	Potato	7	Lightweight CNN (RegNetY- 400MF)	89.87
Gandhi et al. [19]	Several	38	CNN + GAN Augmentation	92.00
Zeng et al. [18]	Citrus	3	DCGAN + Inceptionv3	92.60
Ghosh et al. [10]	Potato	3	VGG19	92.71
Chohan et al. [1]	Tomato	7	Optimized VGG16	94.50
Foysal et al. [8]	Potato, Tomato & Pepper	26	Optimized CNN	98.14
Lamba et al. [14]	Paddy (Rice)	3	GAN Augmentation + CNN	98.23
Trivedi et al. [15]	Tomato	9	DCNN	98.49
Zhang et al. [21]	Tomato	4	Faster RCNN	98.54
Tri-ScaleNet (Ours)	Potato & Tomato	3	cGAN + Multi-Scale Multi-Head CNN	98.62

Table III shows the comparative performance analysis of our proposed model Tri-ScaleNet and the existing methods of plant disease classification. The findings show that the previous methods had mostly used standard CNNs and lightweight frameworks in classifying diverse disease types. But Tri-ScaleNet which integrates cGAN-based data augmentation with a multi-scale CNN framework, achieves the highest classification accuracy of 98.62% on potato and tomato leaf diseases, demonstrating superior discriminative power and stability compared to earlier studies.

G. Deployment

Fig. 9-10 represents the Streamlit interface of the proposed Tri-ScaleNet system. The interface allows users to upload a leaf image and obtain real-time disease predictions along with its confidence scores, while Grad-CAM visualizations highlight disease-affected areas to support explainable decision-making.

Fig. 9: Streamlit interface for real-time disease prediction

2. Explainable AI (Grad-CAM)

Interpretation: The model is detecting concentric rings on the leaf surface.

Fig. 10: Grad-CAM overlays for interpretability

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

A. Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that combining generative learning with multi-scale feature extraction offers a practical and effective solution for plant disease classification. The use of cGAN-based augmentation significantly improved dataset balance and diversity, leading to more stable and reliable model training. At the same time, the multi-scale design of Tri-ScaleNet proved to be effective in handling the wide variations in disease symptom sizes commonly observed in plant leaves.

The experimental results indicate that the proposed approach performs consistently well across different disease categories with minimal confusion between visually similar classes. Visual explanations provided by Grad-CAM further support these results by showing that the model consistently focuses on disease-affected regions rather than irrelevant background objects. Overall, this study highlights the importance of addressing both data quality and feature-scale variation when designing deep learning models for agricultural applications and provides a strong foundation for future advancements in automated plant disease monitoring.

B. Future Scope

Future work will extend Tri-ScaleNet towards multi-crop and multi-disease framework, enabling simultaneous detection of multiple diseases across diverse crop types and making the system suitable for large-scale plant health monitoring. The framework can also be enhanced using few-shot and zero-shot learning, by combining GAN-based augmentation with meta-learning techniques for detecting new or rare diseases using only a limited number of labeled samples. Also, it is possible to include temporal sequences of leaf images which will allow analysis of disease progression and predicting infection in its early stages. These extensions will also enhance scalability, flexibility and practicality of the proposed approach, making it more effective for crop health monitoring.

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